

INVESTIGATION OF OPINIONS AND EXPECTATIONS OF THE PUBLIC STAFF WORKING IN GAZIANTEP GOVERNORSHIP ABOUT RECREATION AND SPORTIVE RECREATION HABITSⁱ

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Abstract:

This study is prepared with the aim of determining the opinions and expectations about recreation and sportive recreation habits of public officials working in the governance of Gaziantep province between 2013-2014. For this study, a sportive recreation scale, which was previously validated and reliable by İc (2004), was used. Descriptive Method was used in the study. A total of 69 people consisting of 21 women and 48 men who worked in the provincial governorship of Gaziantep participated in the survey. As a means of data collection in the survey, questions were asked to determine the demographic characteristics of the participants in the first section and sportive recreation scale was used in the second section. The scale consists of 4 sub-dimensions and 14 items, and a five-point Likert scale is used. SPSS for Windows Version 16.0 package program was used for the statistical analysis of the study data and $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. In the analysis of the data, descriptive statistical methods (Frequency, Percentage, Mean, Standard deviation) were used. Independent sample t-test and Anova test were used in the analysis of hypotheses. The scale was subjected to the reliability test by the Cronbach Alpha statistical method and the study questionnaire was found to be valid at a rate of 0.89. As a descriptive statistic frequency are percentage values are looked at. As a result of the survey, it is found that most of

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the participants in the survey are high school and university graduates and mostly civil servants, they are mostly 41 years old and over, most of them were doing sport as local and amateur or at the school but currently they do not play sports at a great rate and at the same time they do not participate in recreational activities, they play football with the greatest participation as a sporting recreation activity.

Keywords: recreation, opinion and expectation, public staff

1. Introduction

The impact of the industrial revolution has created more free time in human life. For this reason, the increase of leisure time made recreational activities more and more important (Ozturk, 2014). Recreation is one of the main objectives of leisure time evaluation outside of work (Ozdog, 1996). Recreation is an activity in which people participate voluntarily and freely, satisfy and enjoy themselves in their spare time (leisure time) except for what they have to make obligatory life (Hazar, 2009).

According to the classical approach, Recreation is defined as re-creating and renewing voluntary activities after the compulsory work and activities (Kraus, 1985). It is time outside of the business life that the person is absolutely free and independent, that is, when the person engages with an activity that he or she gets rid of necessity for himself or the others and chooses with his own will (Tezcan, 1994).

In general terms, recreation is all entertainment and resting activities that people voluntarily participate in their leisure time with the aim of development and satisfaction motivations (Kirikoglu 2004). People are involved in the events in their spare time, which emerged in various sizes and times in or out of the home, in the open or closed areas, at the workplace or outside, in the city or in rural areas for various purposes such as getting away, relaxing, being happy, air exchanging, riding, health, being together, getting excited. Here, recreation can be expressed as a concept expressing these activities that people do in leisure time (Yetim, 2000).

Recreation refers to leisure time activities that are outside the compulsory work of the person and which, in the manner of use, entitle the individual to free choice, and activities performed by means and methods that vary according to each other, recreation; in developed societies, it has become a tool, not a target to be reached (İc, 2005). On the other hand, as a leisure time activity sport carries only recreational activities with an amateurish purpose (Kocer, 1977). In short, while Sport provides an important area of action in meeting people 's recreational needs, recreation has also

played an important role in the sport's widespread recognition and sporting success (Karakucuk, 1995).

With this study, it was tried to determine the opinions and expectations about recreation and sportive recreation habits of public officials working in the governance of Gaziantep province. I hope that this study which we done will give direction to other public officials and be helpful for researchers working on the same subject.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Population and Sample

Target population of the research is the personnel who work in the governorship of Gaziantep between the years 2013-2014. In this frame, 90 questionnaires were tried to be applied randomly and 69 questionnaires were evaluated. According to these results, the evaluation rate of the questionnaires was 77%.

2.2. Data Collection Tool

Survey technique was used as data collection tool. Survey questions were evaluated with multiple choice questions and Likert type scales (Kaptan, 1998). Within the scope of the necessary literature review about the subject of the study, electronic databases for academic purposes and university libraries were used. Higher Education Council (YOK) documentation center for theses made in Turkey on the subject; For international theses, "ProQuest Dissertations and Theses", an electronic dissertation database of universities abroad, have been utilized.

The questionnaire consists of 2 parts in accordance with the purpose of the study. In the first part, a personal information form was developed by the researcher to reveal the demographics of the participants. In the second part of the study, the attitude scale developed by İc was used (İc, 2004). The scale used for this section consists of 4 sub-dimensions and consists of a total of 14 questions including: thought (5 questions), levels (5 questions), inadequacy (2 questions) and environmental influence (2 questions).

In the first part, questions about demographic information are included. In the second part, a five-point Likert-type scale, in which validity and reliability studies were conducted by İc (2004), was used in order to measure the opinions and expectations of recreational activities of the public personnel working in the governorship.

2.3. Analysis of Data

For the statistical analyzes, SPSS for Windows version 15.0 package program was used and $P < 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant. Factor analysis method was used in the validity and reliability analyzes of the scales. Internal consistency of the scales was determined by Cronbach Alpha values. Frequency, percentage mean and standard deviation values are given as descriptive statistics. For normally distributed variables, Student t-test was used for two independent groups comparison, ANOVA and Tukey multiple comparison tests for more than two independent groups comparison were used.

3. Results

Table 1: Characteristics of the Governorate of employees participating in the study

Variable	Level	f	%
Genders	Male	48	69.6
	Female	21	30.4
Ages	26-30	23	33.2
	31-35	15	21.7
	36-40	10	14.5
	41 years and over	21	30.4
Education status	Primary and secondary school	7	10.1
	High school and balanced	24	34.8
	University and above	15	21.6
Tasks	Retainers	8	11.6
	Officers	54	78.3
	Director or chief	7	10.1

Table 1 shows the distribution of the answers given to questions about personal characteristics of the research group. According to this; Participants majority 69.6 % of the research were men (48) and 34.4% of the participants were women (21), when the age distribution was examined, it was found that the maximum age was 26-30 years (33.2%), when we look at the educational status, it is seen that the majority was 24 (34.8%) high school graduates and the majority 54 (78.3%) were employed as civil servants.

Table 2: Sportive Recreation Levels of Governorate of employees participating in the study

Variable	Level	f	%
Previous Sports Activities	No	25	36.2
	School neighborhood	22	31.9
	Amateur	22	31.9
Current Sportive Activities	Yes	11	16.2
	No	22	32.4
	Sometimes	35	51.5
Participation in Sportive Recreational Activities	Yes	6	8.7
	No	19	27.5
	Sometimes	44	63.8
Sportive Recreation activities they participate in most	Football	17	53.1
	Others	15	46.9
Previous Sports Activities	Fighting sports	35	92.1
	Mountaineering	2	7.9

According to Table 2, when sportive recreation levels of governorate of employees participating in the study were examined, it was seen that 25 people (36.2%) did not play sports before, by looking at current sportive activities it was seen that the 44 people (63.8%) from the participants did play sports sometimes, also football is the sportive recreation activity that 47 people (53.1%) among participants played most, and it was seen that fighting sports are sport that 35 people (92.1%). Among participants disliked most.

Table 3: Opinions about involvement in sportive recreation activities of Governorate of employees participating in the study

	I totally disagree		I do not agree		Undecided		I agree		I totally agree	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
I would like to participate in sports recreation activities to get a social environment	12	17.4	9	13.0	13	18.8	27	40.3	6	9.0
I would like to participate in sports recreation activities to gain prestige	10	15.2	16	24.2	15	22.7	20	30.3	5	7.6
I would like to participate in sports recreation to relax in spiritual and mental terms	10	14.9	7	10.4	8	11.9	27	40.3	15	22.4
I like to participate in such activities because i like sports recreation	9	13.6	6	9.1	15	22.7	24	36.4	12	18.2
I would like to participate in sports recreational activities in terms of health	11	16.4	7	10.4	3	4.5	33	49.3	13	19.4

According to Table 3, when opinions about involvement in sportive recreation activities of Governorate of employees participating in the study were examined, it was seen that 27 people (40.3%) do sports to get a social environment and the same percentage do sports for relaxing both spiritual and mental, 20 people (30.3 %) do sports to gain prestige, 24 people (36.4 %) do sports because they like and 33 people (49.3%) do sports for being healthy.

Table 4: Levels of involvement in sportive recreation activities of Governorate of employees participating in the study

	I totally disagree		I do not agree		Undecided		I agree		I totally agree	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
I would like to participate in sports recreation activities with my family	13	19.7	7	10.6	8	12.1	25	39.7	13	19.7
I would like to participate in sports recreation activities with my friends	10	14.5	6	8.7	8	11.6	31	44.9	14	20.3
I would like to participate in individual sports recreation activities	11	16.4	10	14.9	8	11.9	29	43.3	9	13.4
I would like to participate in bilateral sporting recreation activities	10	15.4	12	18.5	11	16.9	24	39.9	8	12.3
I would like to participate in recreational sporting activities in teams	13	19.7	9	13.6	15	22.7	22	33.3	7	10.6

According to Table 4, when levels of involvement in sportive recreation activities of Governorate of employees participating in the study were examined, it was seen that 25 people (39.7 %) choose sport with their family, 31 (44.9 %) choose sport with their friends, 29 people (43.3 %) prefer individual sports, 24 people (39.9 %) prefer bilateral sports and the highly prefer the choice of "I agree" to sportive recreational activities in teams.

Table 5: Inabilities of involvement in sportive recreation activities of Governorate of employees participating in the study

	I totally disagree		I do not agree		Undecided		I agree		I totally agree	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
I cannot attend the activities because I do not have enough financial means	13	19.7	9	13.6	15	22.7	22	33.3	7	10.6
I cannot attend the activities because I do not have enough time	12	17.9	13	19.4	12	17.9	17	25.4	13	19.4

According to Table 5, when inabilities of involvement in sportive recreation activities of Governorate of employees participating in the study were examined, it was seen that 22 people (33,3 %) cannot do sport because of not having enough money and 17 people (25.4%) cannot do sport because of not having enough time.

Table 6: Environmental impacts on sportive recreation activities of Governorate of employees participating in the study

	I totally disagree		I do not agree		Undecided		I agree		I totally agree	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
I cannot go to the activities because there are not enough spaces around	8	11.9	16	23.9	15	22.4	14	20.9	14	20.9
I cannot attend because there is no formation for recreational activities around	5	7.4	17	25.0	16	23.5	15	22.1	15	22.1

According to Table 6, when environmental impacts on sportive recreation activities of Governorate of employees participating in the study were examined, it was seen that 14 people (20.9 %) cannot do sport because of not having enough spaces around and 15 people (22.1 %) cannot do sport because of not having formation recreational activities around.

Table 7: The Average of the Sub-dimensions of the Opinions and Expectations about the Recreation and recreation habits of the governorship officials

	n	$\bar{x}$	S.D.
Opinions	69	3.29	0.95
Levels		3.22	1.13
Inabilities		3.00	1.18
Environmental impacts		3.21	1.16

According to Table 7, it is seen that the highest expectations of governorship officials about opinions dimension (Avg. 3.29) and the lowest expectations about inabilities.

Table 8: Relation between sportive recreations habits according to gender and recreation opinions and expectations of the governorship officials

		n	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	t	p
Opinions	Female	21	3.33	0.69	0.43	0.66
	Male	48	3.23	1.05		
Levels	Female	21	3.42	0.97	0.96	0.33
	Male	48	3.13	1.18		

Inabilities	Female	21	2.86	1.07	0.69	0.48
	Male	48	3.07	1.22		
Environmental impacts	Female	21	3.10	0.97	0.52	0.60
	Male	48	3.26	1.24		

Significant at P <0.5 level

According to Table 8, there was no significant difference in the average of sportive recreation levels sub-dimensions of the Governorships officers according to gender ($p > 0.05$).

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The results of this study on "Investigation of Opinions and Expectations of the Public Staff Working In Gaziantep Governorship about Recreation and Sportive Recreation Habits" can be summarized as follows:

Of the 69 public officials who participated in the survey, 48 were men and 21 were women. While the proportion of males is 69.6%, the proportion of females is 30.4%.

According to the answers given by governorship officials the participating in the survey, while the most favorite sport was frequently answered with football (43.6%), handball (1.8) had the lowest average. This study is similar to some studies in the literature. As a result of the study conducted by İç (2004), the most popular sport branch was found as football (47.7%) (İç, 2004). As a result of studying Karakucuk, there are sport activities in the first place like walking (20.6 %) and football (17.7 %) (Karakucuk, 1995).

It is thought that most of the participants choose football in their leisure time because economically walking and football activities do not bring a financial burden. The findings of the study conducted by Pular on the activities of the residents in the credit institution of the country are parallel to the findings of our research (Pular, 2003). In the survey conducted by Bulut, football is seen as the most preferred activity at the beginning of the leisure activities preferred in leisure time (Bulut, 2002).

When opinions about involvement in sportive recreation activities of Governorate of employees participating in the study were examined, it was seen that officers prefer to do sports because of liking to do or being healthy among the dimensions such as to get a social environment, for relaxing both spiritual and mental, to gain prestige, like to do and for being healthy. This study is similar to some studies in the literature. Arıkan and Ozkokeli, in their study "A Study on Leisure Activities of Police Academy Students", found that police academics think that their participation in

sports leisure time activities had a positive effect on their health (Arikan and Ozkokeli, 2002). As a result of Havighurst's work "Leisure Time Activities of Middle Age Persons", leisure activities for men and women between the ages of 40-70 have been identified as psychologically significant, and participation in sports activities is only meant to stay healthy (Havighurst, 1957).

When levels of involvement in sportive recreation activities of Governorate of employees participating in the study were examined, it was seen that officers prefer to do sports in team among the dimensions such as sport with their family, sport with their friends, individual sports, bilateral sports and teams sports. This study differs from some studies the literature in. Research by Marcus and Francis found that young people prefer parks to go alone with besides prefer to go with their family and friends. The reason for the difference in this study is thought to be due to age (Marcus and Francis, 1998). As a result of Ward Thompson's work, it appears that young people prefer to be individualized as much as socialization (Ward Thompson, 2002).

When inabilities of involvement in sportive recreation activities of Governorate of employees participating in the study were examined, it was seen that officers cannot do sport because of not having enough money and cannot do sport because of not having enough time. This study is similar to some studies in the literature and also at the same time differs from some studies. As a result of the study conducted by İc, 52.5% of the survey participants indicated that they had sufficient financial means to participate in the activities and 38.0% had not enough time to participate in the activities (İc, 2004).

When environmental impacts on sportive recreation activities of Governorate of employees participating in the study were examined, it was seen that officers prefer mostly dimensions of not having enough spaces around and not having formation recreational activities around. This study is similar to some studies in the literature. As a result of the study conducted by İc, it was seen that 42.4% of the subjects participating in the survey stated that they could not participate in the activities because there was not enough space in their surroundings and 51.5% had no formation for recreational activities in their surroundings.

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